

Animal Supplementary Feed Workshop

**Lincoln, New Zealand
December 2017**

Presentations and Notes
from the
Animal Supplementary Feed Workshop

Lincoln, New Zealand

5 December 2017

The workshop was planned and organised by:

Dr Bill Griffin, The New Zealand Institute for Plant & Food Research Limited

David Green, PGG Wrightson Seeds Limited

Foreword and Acknowledgments

The New Zealand pastoral industries are a very significant contributor to GDP and export earnings. Supplementary feeds are a strategic component of this industry. In particular, whether grazed or harvested for later use, these feeds supplement during periods of high demand and during low supply.

This document is intended to capture the presentations and thoughts of participants from a wide range of organisations involved in supplementary feed from supply to use, research to regulation. We particularly thank the participants and also the organisations they represent for providing the financial support to attend and participate.

Although a lot is lost by simply capturing presentation slides rather than the full content of a presentation, we hope that at least some value can be gained from refreshing memories of specific presentations.

Editor: Warrick Nelson, The New Zealand Institute for Plant & Food Research Limited

Doi: [10.5281/zenodo.1305408](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1305408)

Cover: Livestock grazing kale, North Canterbury

CONTENTS

Introduction	1
Programme	2
Workshop Presentations	4
DairyNZ: Ina Pinxterhuis.....	4
Animal nutrition and welfare: Prof Pablo Gregorini, Lincoln University	7
Foundation for Arable Research (FAR): Ivan Lawrie	9
Regional Councils: Ian Brown (Environment Canterbury)	13
The Farmer Operator: Mark Slee, Melrose Farm	17
The Farming Consultant: Miranda Hunter, Roslyn Consultancy Ltd.....	18
The Corporate Farming Enterprise: Paul McGill (Landcorp).....	21
Challenges and Opportunities	23
Group discussion session	23
Verbal reporting back session.....	24
Collation 1	25
Collation 2	26
Associated material	27
Participants	30

Sheep grazing Pallaton Raphno®. Pallaton is the first new forage brassica New Zealand farming has seen since the 1980s and delivers impressive agronomic attributes including high yield from multiple grazings, improved insect tolerance and plant persistence under multiple grazings.

INTRODUCTION

Warrick Nelson

Supplementary feeds provide an important contribution to animal nutrition in New Zealand. The bulk of these supplementary feeds apply to dairy cows. Recent statistics (DairyNZ 2016) indicate that dairy cows receive about 10% of feed from NZ grown crops, slightly more than 50% of the total supplementary feed given. Of the NZ grown crops, about 37% is eaten by grazing, the balance is harvested crops. NZ grown feeds are grown on just less than 800 000 ha, although this area will include small amounts of grains for human consumption.

Animal products are a significant proportion of human diets. In the context for New Zealand the biggest component is our dairy industry. The bulk of dairy feed comes from grazing pasture, traditionally ryegrass plus other species such as clover. However, there are typically seasonal requirements when other feed supplies are required. Occasionally there is also the need to bring in feed for animals because of damage or loss of access to pastures, such as flooding or drought events.

Crops for cows (and other animals) is a significant use of land. Current drivers of land use are aiming to target higher value land use in terms of financial returns. This frequently implies horticultural crops. However, availability of capital and people with suitable capability and interest is not immediately available to make such wholesale changes. Food from animals is frequently a good use of products grown on this land, especially when also taking into account overall market risk for a significantly export-driven economy.

At a national level, the equation of value from land needs to take into account all value associated with land use. This includes tourism value, and downstream value, rather than simply farmgate prices, including potential value-added processing procedures. From a plant production perspective, animal products represent a downstream value-added processing step. This leads further to reviewing the value of land use not simply in dollar returns and environmental and social effects, but also considering human food value per hectare (Cassidy et al. 2013). While it is true that some crops could be a direct source of human food, in the NZ dairy context, this is very seldom the case. The perceived “waste” of calories processing through an animal system is not necessarily applicable for either current crops grown or foreseeable land uses.

As noted in the presentations and workshop outcomes, supplementary feed expectations are shifting in the NZ dairy industry. Imported PKE (palm kernel expeller) remains an important product, but concerns of quality and biosecurity risk have caused some farmers to revise their use of this product. To this end, local growing of supplementary feed may be seen as a lower biosecurity risk and may provide better security of supply at critical times.

Cassidy, Emily S, Paul C West, James S Gerber, and Jonathan A Foley. 2013. “Redefining Agricultural Yields: From Tonnes to People Nourished per Hectare.” *Environmental Research Letters* 8 (3): 034015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/8/3/034015>.

DairyNZ. 2016. “Feed Use in the NZ Dairy Industry.” MPI Technical Paper 2017/53. <https://www.mpi.govt.nz/dmsdocument/20897-feed-use-in-the-nz-dairy-industry>.

PROGRAMME

Fitzgerald Room, PFR, Lincoln, 9.30am – 4.30pm

Workshop goals:

1. Understanding the role of supplementary feeds in our dairy and livestock industries - current and future opportunities and challenges given animal welfare, climate, environmental and regulatory constraints.
2. Agree the top 10 current and future (10+ years) challenges/opportunities and steps to overcome/capitalise.

Audience:

Maximum 50 invited to represent:

Users: DairyNZ, Beef+Lamb
Producers: FAR
Regulators: Regional Councils
R&D: PFR, AgR, LU, PGGW

Facilitator: Craig Osborne

- Mediate all sessions
- Summarise key challenges/opportunities from each presentation
- Run table discussions on developing a roadmap to get from now to this 10+ year future and the market/regulatory/public/R&D steps required to overcome or achieve these challenges/opportunities, meet public expectations on environmental impact and maximise plant/animal productivity within climate boundaries

Workshop structure/agenda:

Morning:

- 1st session: Industry reps - 20 min, plus another 10min facilitated discussion. Each has been asked to be provocative; setting the scene for the component of the industry they represent; current and future (10+ years) challenges/opportunities; and to identify up to 5 key future challenges/opportunities and why. They will be expected to lead an afternoon breakout group to discuss the key future challenges/opportunities identified after the morning presentations.
- 2nd session: Farming reps – 15 min, plus another 5 min discussion. Each has been asked to describe how they are producing/supplying/using supplementary feeds within their farming enterprises now; their future targets/plans; and the support they are looking for to achieve these targets.

Programme:

9.30	DairyNZ	Ina Pinxterhuis
10.00	Animal nutrition and welfare	Prof Pablo Gregorini
10.30	Morning tea	
10.45	FAR	Ivan Lawrie
11.15	Regional Councils	Ian Brown - Ecan
11.45	The Farmer Operator	Mark Slee
12.05	The Farming Consultant	Miranda Hunter
12.25	The Corporate Farming Enterprise	Paul McGill, LandCorp
12.45	Lunch	

1.30 Breakout group discussions

- The facilitator will para-phrase the key messages/challenges/opportunities for the 10+ year horizon from all preceding sessions – top 10
- The audience will be organised into groups (maximum 6-7 each), led by one of the morning speakers
- Each group will be given the top 10 challenges/opportunities, tease them out if necessary, then develop a 10 year roadmap from now to this 10+ year future and the market/regulatory/public/R&D steps required to overcome or achieve the challenges/opportunities, meet public expectations on environmental impact and maximise plant/animal productivity within climate boundaries
- Sticky note format

2.30 Reporting back. Each group leader to present their roadmap

3.00 Afternoon tea

3.15 Facilitator wrap-up

3.45 Finish

Next steps:

A team (coordinated by David Green: Mike Beare, Paul Johnstone, Ivan Lawrie, Alan Stewart, Derek Woodfield) to take these roadmaps and develop an action plan – who needs to do what by when.

The R&D components should include crop breeding and sustainable productivity targets; animal performance and welfare issues; and environmental impact monitoring and mitigation.

Potential research collaborations and funding channels should be named.

WORKSHOP PRESENTATIONS

DairyNZ: Ina Pinxterhuis

Presenter key points:

Identify next-generation forage crops and management systems that:

1. Increase harvestable ME/ha
2. Increase intake and MS production/cow, i.e. less substitution
3. Are resilient to pests, diseases and climate variability
4. Create feeds safe for animals (anti-nutritionals, WSC, amino acids, minerals)
5. Enhance milk composition for value—add products

AND they need to be better than pasture and fit in farming systems that balance workforce and animal welfare, environment, profit, production and consumer and community expectations.

Supplementary feed in NZ dairying

Animal Supplementary Feed Workshop 5 December 2017
Ina Pinxterhuis

Outline

- Changes in the last 20 years
- Current dairy systems
- Current research focus
- Dairy Tomorrow
- Key opportunities

NZ dairy has grown, a lot

From 1995 – 2015:

- Cows: 2.9 M to 5 M (+70%)
- Area: 1.2 M to 1.75 M hectares (+45%)
- Milk production: 8.1 B to 18.6 B milksolids (+129%)
- Exported product: \$3 B to \$12 B (+338%)

Edwards, 2017

Growth not the same everywhere

Edwards, 2017

Milk production/ha grown as well

- Increase dependent on climatic constraints and water availability
- Contribution of crops: summer/winter feed, in-shed feeding

Current dairy systems are diverse

System 1 – All grass self-contained, 100% home grown feed with all adult stock on the dairy platform

No feed is imported. No supplement fed to the herd except supplement harvested off the effective milking area and dry cows are not grazed off the effective milking area.

System 2 – 90-99% of total feed is home grown feed.

1-10% of feed is imported either as supplement or grazing off for wintering dry cows.

System 3 – 80-89% of total feed is home grown feed

11-20% of total feed imported to extend lactation (typically autumn feed) and for wintering dry cows

System 4 – 70-79% of total feed is home grown feed.

21-30% of feed imported and used at both ends of lactation and for wintering dry cows

System 5 – 50 to 69% of total feed is home grown feed.

More than 31% of feed imported and used throughout lactation. Feed imported could be greater than 50%.

DairyNZ Facts and Figures, 2017

Key strategic decisions by farmer

- Calving date
- Stocking rate/cow live weight
- Milk production per cow

→ Determines relationship between feed supply and feed demand

Can adjust feed demand by early culling or drying off

Role of crops

- Fill feed gaps to meet animal demand
- Increase milk production/ha
- Meet environmental obligations

Does it, if all hectares are counted?

- Cool winters
- Reduced N intake when fed in winter
- Dry summers
- Moderate N content to supplement pasture during summer and early autumn

But need to limit N losses during crop growth, crop use and after harvest

Current DairyNZ crop research investment

FRNL, SFF, NARF, SDH

- Reduce N intake, improve ME intake
maintain/improve animal performance & health + reduce urinary N excretion
- Improve DM yield and N uptake
- Match soil N supply and plant demand following cultivation or winter grazing
- Reduce treading damage
- Maximise value of slurry/manure
- Optimise pasture-based farm system performance
costs, labour, milk production, milk quality, animal body condition

DairyNZ

Fodder beet reduces urinary N excretion

	Late lactation cows	Pasture	Past+23%FB	Past+45%FB
N intake (g)	460	407	317	**
Faecal N (g)	148	139	131	ns
Milk N (g)	57	64	67	ns
Urine N (g)	205	155	112	***

Risks to animals:

- Acidosis
- Mineral supply (P)
- Amino acids

Forages for Reduced Nitrate Leaching; Waghorn, Dalley et al., 2017

DairyNZ

Presenter key points:

1. Biochemical heterogeneity and environmental impact
2. Functional diversity of diets...variety and its real meaning
3. Animal emotions and experiences/ animal personalities
4. Systems re-design

The presentation included material from current student research activity, but largely includes extension of work already published. The following published papers indicate the direction of work included in the presentation.

Grazing management: setting the table, designing the menu and influencing the diner

Pastoral livestock-production systems are under increasing environmental, social and consumer pressures to reduce environmental impacts and to enhance biodiversity and animal welfare. At the same time, farmers face the challenge of managing grazing, which is intimately linked with profitability. Recent advances in understanding grazing patterns and nutritional ecology may help alleviate such pressures. For instance, by managing grazing to (1) manipulate links between ingestive–digestive decisions and temporal patterns of nutrient excretion, (2) provide phytochemically diverse diets at appropriate temporal (the menu) and spatial (the table) scales and (3) influence the behaviour of animals (the diners) on the basis of their specific ‘personalities’ and needs, to overcome or enhance animal differences, thereby enhancing their and farm productivity and welfare, as well as our health. Under pastoral systems, synergies between animals’ and farmers’ grazing decisions have the potential to offer greater benefits to the animal, the environment and the farm than does simple and parsimonious grazing management based on a single component of the system. In the present review, we look at grazing and its management through an alternate lens, drawing ideas and hypotheses to stimulate thinking, dialogue and discussions that we anticipate will evolve into innovative research programs and grazing strategies. To do so, we combined experimental and observational studies from a wide range of disciplines with simulation-modelling exercises. We envisage a more holistic approach to manage grazing based on recent advances in the understanding of the nutritional ecology of grazing animals, and propose management practices that may enable pastoral livestock-production systems to evolve continually as complex creative systems.

<https://doi.org/10.1071/AN16637>

Screening for diets that reduce urinary nitrogen excretion and methane emissions while maintaining or increasing production by dairy cows

Farmers face complex decisions at the time to feed animals, trying to achieve production goals while contemplating social and environmental constraints. Our purpose was to facilitate such decision making for pastoral dairy farmers, aiming to reduce urinary N (UN) and methane emissions (CH₄), while maintaining or increasing milk production (MP). There is a number of feeds the farmers can choose from and combine. We used 50 feeds (forages and grains) combined systematically in different proportions producing 11,526 binary diets. Diets were screened, using an a posteriori approach and a Pareto front (PF) analysis of model (Molly) outputs. The objective was to identify combinations with the best possible compromise (i.e. frontier) between UN, CH₄, and MP. Using high MP and low UN as objective functions, PF included 10, 14, 12 and 50 diets, for non-lactating, early-, mid- and late-lactation periods, with cereals and beets featuring strongly. Using the same objective functions, but including ryegrass as dietary base PF included 2, 4, 8 and 4 diets for those periods. Therefore, from a wide range of diets, farmers could choose from few

feeds combined into binary diets to reduce UN while maintaining or increasing MP. If the intention is maintaining pasture-based systems, there are fewer suitable options. Reducing UN will simply require dilution of N supplied by pasture by supplementing low N conserved forages. The results also evidence the risk of pollution swapping, reaching the frontier means arriving at a point where trade-off decisions need to be made. Any further reduction in UN implies an increment in CH₄, or reduction in CH₄ emissions increases UN. There is no perfect diet to optimize all objectives simultaneously; but if the current diet is not in the frontier some options can offset pollution swapping. The choice is with the farmers and conditioned by their context.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.01.203>

Foundation for Arable Research (FAR): Ivan Lawrie

Presenter key points:

1. Winter grazing in arable systems: managing the Impacts
2. Cereal silage in the rotation: production and quality
3. Grains: A possible solution
4. Catch crops, cover crops and effluent use
5. Biosecurity threats in supplementary feeds

Incorporating Arable Feed Products.

Animal Supplementary Feed Workshop

Ivan Lawrie -FAR

5th December 2017

FAR ADDING VALUE TO THE BUSINESS OF CROPPING

FAR FOCUS
Foundation For Arable Research Issue 10 June 2013

Crops for Cows

ISSUE 10

- Cropping sequences on the dairy platform
- The environmental benefits of crops in dairy systems
- Maize silage: The other side of the coin
- Faba beans for winter and spring production in Hawkes Bay and Canterbury
- Future directions

Five key areas.

- **Winter grazing** in arable systems: managing the Impacts.
- **Cereal silage** in the rotation: production and quality.
- **Grains**: A possible solution.
- **Catch crops**, cover crops and effluent use.
- **Biosecurity** threats in supplementary feeds.

FAR

Dairy Grazing

FAR

Winter Grazing \$

	Kale	Fodder Beet	Oat
Seed	\$99.00	\$333.96	\$180.00
Drilling	\$80.00	\$170.00	\$120.00
Herbicides	\$55.63	\$385.28	\$24.00
Pesticides	\$17.10	\$16.85	-
Fertilisers	\$607.27	\$719.54	\$161.77
Irrigation	\$160.00	\$92.00	\$64.00
Other Machinery ops.	\$335.34	\$408.01	\$47.00
Total cost /ha	\$1,354.34	\$2,125.64	\$596.77
Yield TDM/ha*	14.8	21.3	5.5
Cost/kg	\$0.09	\$0.10	\$0.11

* Based on field data – Mid Canterbury. Indicative for trends only.
** Price per kg ranges from \$0.25 to \$0.30 (different arrangements)

Dairy Grazing

FAR

Dairy Grazing related research (FAR)

- Forages for Reduced Nitrate Leaching.
- SFF- Dairy Grazing on Arable Farms
- Fodderbeet establishment trials 2015.
- Fodderbeet irrigation trials 2015.
- Fodderbeet Agronomy SFF 2016

FAR

Risk Management Guide for Intensive Winter Grazing on Arable Farms

Yes/no	Risk factor	Risk of nitrate leaching	Risk of P and sediment losses	Risk of compaction and pugging	Risk management options
	Light soils (sandy, stony)	✓			1
	Heavy soils		✓	✓	1, 2, 4, 6
	Poor soil structure		✓	✓	1, 2, 4, 6
	Steep slopes		✓		1, 4, 5
	Critical sources (waterways, natural drainage streams)		✓		1, 5, 6
	High stocking density (cows/ha/day)	✓		✓	3, 6
	High soil residual N levels	✓			1, 2, 3
	High protein level in feed	✓			3, 6
	Lack of knowledge or skills in staff managing winter grazing		✓	✓	1, 5, 6
	Consecutive winter cropping	✓	✓	✓	2
	High rainfall (all above risk factors are intensified with high rainfall)	✓	✓	✓	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6

Risk Management Options

1. Paddock assessment	Some paddocks may need to be avoided completely. Only graze high risk areas in dry conditions. Cows should graze early in the season before they get saturated, and light soils later in the season after the highest risk of drainage. Avoid grazing at the top of the slope and work downhill. When near waterways, begin grazing away from the critical source and work towards it, leaving an access strip to the pond.
2. Crop rotation and subsoiling	Allow paddocks to receive between grazing events (soil prone to compaction should have longer periods between winter forage crops). Fit the crop rotation so that it helps break weed, disease, and pest cycles. Manage between crops to meet crop demand. Use a crop that can utilize nitrogen in soil (barley, grass) as soon as soil conditions are suitable.
3. Crop selection and management	Manage between crops to meet crop demand. If grazing a high yielding crop, use relative management strategies (see number 6). Choose a lower yielding crop (barley, vetch, forage maize) to reduce stock density requirements. Unchecked nutrient quality of crops, and equipment accordingly (e.g. take in high in protein but low in fibre, are supplemental feeds but not grazed).
4. Feed presentation	Place bales of straw or forage throughout paddock for break feeding to alleviate the need to stock heavy equipment on vulnerable soils. Fit bales low in dry conditions and feed of the paddock when needed.
5. Staff training	Ensure staff responsible for managing grazing are up-to-date with management strategies to avoid soil compaction and pugging.
6. Managing grazing on vulnerable soils	Set up paddocks in a contract if staff from other farms are managing grazing. Split the herd into small groups before and during grazing to increase amount of equipment use, and feed out in less vulnerable areas. Stock levels and use responsible water troughs to minimise feed traffic on bare soils. Split the herd into multiple groups to reduce grazing density. Have a stand-off paddock or pad in very wet conditions.

FAR

Whole Crop Cereal Silage

- Provides a good option in arable rotations.
- Good range of material available.
- Can be used as a catch crop for dairy.
- Good gross margin per day returns.
- ME and other quality attributes underestimated.

But:

- Timing is critical – reliance on contractors.
- Sampling is difficult
- Treated as a poor cousin to grain crop.
- Hard to fund research.

FAR

Managing whole crop cereal silage yield and profitability of autumn-sown crops

M.E. Armandin¹, J.M. de Ruiter², S. Maley² and N.B. Pyke¹

An assessment of metabolisable energy and quality of barley whole crop silage

de Ruiter, J., Gibbs J

August 2017

CONCLUSIONS

1. Use of NIRS predictions of whole crop silage quality (digestibility and ME) not validated against an *in vivo* test continue to perpetuate erroneous estimations of quality of WCS.

FAR

Lab tests sell cereal silage short

Andrew Swallow

Plant and Food Research's John de Ruiter with one of the barley silage samples used in the research.

"Whole-crop cereal silage really has been short-changed." For growers WCS has the advantage it is off the paddock several weeks before it would be if taken for grain. This means the land is available earlier for a new crop. There's also the option of taking the crop as green-chop silage in November, which creates additional flexibility for growers. Together with its flexibility and a solution for the perceived feed quality

Whole-crop cereal silage (WCS) could be worth reconsidering as a feed judging by results from Plant & Food Research showing quality tests have short-changed WCS for decades. Comparison of near infrared reflectance (NIRS) analysis of barley WCS with live animal (*n-vivo*) digestion of the same

Grains: Part of the solution...

- Complementary rather than supplementary?
- NZ world leader in grain yields.
- Local, traceable, efficient, storable.
- Can be a catch crop.
- Is PKE going away?

On social media this week...

I doubt that would work for you. You'd have to give in before they would. PKE is shit, pay a bit extra for a decent feed that will give you a better return on your investment, lower the stocking rate & everything will work out better in the long run. (I don't mean you personally)

Regional feed prices - week ending December 2

Free Prices	Last week		Average	2 weeks ago	1 year ago
	Low	High			
Wheat-Milling					
Canterbury	330	380	353	353	327
Wheat-Feed					
Canterbury	360	390	378	379	279
Southland	350	410	400	400	310
Manawatu	380	475	411	406	365
Barley-Feed					
Canterbury	360	400	383	385	265
Southland	370	410	403	403	305
Manawatu	385	475	437	423	350
Oats-Feed					
Southland	385	410	380	380	400
Canterbury	300	350	316	318	370
Maize-Grain					
Manawatu	400	485	448	424	354
Waikato	400	445	443	421	360

Palm Kernel Expeller (PKE)

	Last week	2 weeks ago	1 year ago
Canterbury	271	267	230
Manawatu	298	272	257
Waikato	265	269	224
Southland	272	274	231

SFF Proposal 2017

"Environmental benefits of Arable Feeds"

- Outlines multiple solutions
- Case studies
- Sampling
- Modelling
- FAR, Feds, Dairy NZ, GSTA, Lincoln Uni.

Catch Crops / Cover Crops

- Their fit in arable systems.
- Limitations.
- End Use.

Biosecurity in Feed.

- External and internal threats.
- Avoidable threats.
- Managing the risk.
- Mitigation.
- Cost of response. SGRR.

THANK YOU
Ivan.Lawrie@far.org.nz
@IvanLawrie_FAR

Regional Councils: Ian Brown (Environment Canterbury)

Presenter key points:

1. Farming within nutrient limits changes the game
2. Supplementary feeds are part of the solution
3. Farming practices, feed crops, and environmental impacts
4. Farming is in a state of rapid change
5. It's all about people

Contents

- Setting the scene
- Farming within limits changes the game
- Supplementary feeds are part of the solution
- Impacts of the feeds that you grow
- Farming is in a state of rapid change
- Environment and business risk

Environment Canterbury
Regional Council

The 'End Game'

Environment

Business

Consumers

It's all about:

- Transparency
- Authenticity
- Integrity

Environment Canterbury
Regional Council

National Policy Statement Freshwater Management

Maintain and improve ...

Environment Canterbury
Regional Council

Land & Water Forum Good Management Practices

Environment Canterbury Regional Council

The CWMS

- Origins in 1999 Canterbury Strategic Water Study
- 2008 Canterbury Mayoral Forum took ownership
- Endorsed by all Councils – Nov 2009-Feb 2010
- Vision and Principles
- Targets
 - what to be achieved 2015, 2020 and 2040
- Concept of parallel development
- Local and regional committees

Environment Canterbury Regional Council

How Do We Regulate?

Environment Canterbury Regional Council

Why Limits and GMP?

Environment Canterbury Regional Council

Point 1

- **Farming within a limit changes the game**
 - Farming within nutrient limits is here to stay
 - Limit is a limit – will impact seasonal and longer term farm management decisions
 - Measured using Overseer – used by half of regional councils to manage nutrient losses from farms
 - Supplementary feeds – one of the inputs.

Environment Canterbury Regional Council

OVERSEER®

- Models the flow of nutrients on a farm.
- Optimise farm production minimise environmental impact.
- Being used by regulators to drive farmer behaviour change

Environment Canterbury Regional Council

OVERSEER® Nutrient Budgets – strengths/weaknesses

- Allows the impact of changing the farm system to be analysed e.g. stock, fertiliser, supplements.
- Its use in regulation drives innovation towards nutrient efficient farming systems.
- Uses readily available and auditable information.

Item	Value
Water input	1000000
Atmospheric losses	50000
Nutrient removed in product	10000
Nutrient input	100000
Nutrient losses	50000
Nutrient transfers	10000

But...

- Requires complex regulatory policy to manage model updates.
- Resource hungry to implement.
- Constant change results in misunderstanding and mistrust.

Environment Canterbury Regional Council

OVERSEER®

- Why use?
 - Allows focus on nutrients exported from farm and into environment
 - Provides cost-effective estimates of N loss where measurement impractical/unaffordable
 - Allows farmers freedom to farm within limits, make choices as to how to meet

Environment Canterbury Regional Council

Point 2

- **Supplementary feeds - part of the solution?**

- Various options for reducing N losses from farms – changes in supplementary feeds one of these.

N reduction options – beyond GMP

- Cow Genetics
- Optimal cow condition
- **Low protein supplements**
 - Grain
 - Fodder beet – spring/autumn in situ
 - Fodder beet in autumn with pasture
 - Maize – bought in + home grown
- Mop-up crop
- Reduce stock numbers
- Winter cows on platform - fodder beet
- Spread effluent over larger area
- Slow release N fertilisers
- **Restricted grazing – feed/stand-off pad**
- Increase riparian buffer
- Fully integrated system

Using low-protein supplements

- Model farm in study uses ~ 600 kg/cow grass silage as supplement
- Replacing with lower protein feed (grain, fodder beet) gives reductions of ~ 5-10% at little or no cost, possibly saving
- Fodder beet has several options, e.g. autumn feeding on pasture
- Number of unknowns incl. animal health

A note of caution

- "No point putting a whole lot of low N feed in to reduce N losses in a scenario when it isn't feasible – need to understand impacts on farm system.
- Still need to know the key drivers of N loss on each property and address the most cost effective one first. No point messing round with supplementary feed if you are still applying water inefficiently."

Charlotte Glass - AgriMagic

Point 3

- **Feed itself may not be a problem but practices associated with growing or using it may be.**

- Farm practices – risks and environmental impacts
 - Cultivation
 - Fertilizer use
 - Grazing
 - Movement of heavy machinery
- Farm environment plans – one of the tools

Farm environment plans

- Tool that will help you manage the environmental impacts of your farming activities
- FEP content set through LWRP Schedule 7
- Includes assessment of risks & Objectives & Targets
- Emphasis on:
 - implementing good management practices
 - Systems & processes & business efficiencies
- OVERSEER nutrient budget also required

Cultivation and waterways

Grazing of the critical source areas

Strategic grazing vs Traditional

Strategic grazing - cows entered at the top end of the paddock; strip grazed moving in a downhill direction; protection of the CSA; back-fencing every 4-5 days; final time-restricted grazing of the CSA when soil conditions were suitable.

Traditional grazing - cows entered at the lower end of the paddock; strip grazed, moving in an uphill direction; no protection of the CSA; no back-fencing.

Losses of sediment and P in surface runoff

	Sediment loss kg/ha	Total P loss kg/ha
Control grazing	6635	6.9
Strategic grazing	656	1.2
Reduction	90%	83%

Point 4

- **The farming world is changing rapidly**

- Farming world where sustainability defines the farming conversation
- Technology change
- Substitute products
- Consumers and local populations who are not convinced by the rhetoric
- What was considered good practice 10 years ago may not be good practice today – pace of change is increasing
- What does all this mean for those that supply and support the farming sector?

Point 5

- **Environmental management is an integral part of business management**

- Good systems & processes are key to good business & the management of environmental risks
- Can't consider the environment in isolation from everything else that is happening in the business
- Tools available that can help in management of environmental risk – FEPs, Overseer etc
- People – hearts and minds and skills – the key

Questions?

The Farmer Operator: Mark Slee, Melrose Farm

Presenter key points:

1. Need simple systems
2. Low risk for animal health e.g. nitrates, bloaij/acidosis
3. High yielding and high utilisation
4. Good environmental and animal welfare outcomes (somewhere dry to sit down and shelter)
5. Easy to grow (more resistant to diseases)
6. High in feed value (issue for cereal silage i.e. not ideally suited for milking cows)

History: Brassicas at Melrose Farm

- > 1980-1990 Winter 100 day rotation, grazing off on cropping farms
- > 1990-2000 Kale & Oats Winter grazing with ryegrass straw
- > 2000-2007 Semi self contained growing kale and introducing Fodder Beet
- > 2007-2017 Fodder Beet area increased to present 80ha Fodder Beet & 6Ha Swedes, 17ha Kale
- > Winter 2018 70ha Swedes, 30 ha Fodder Beet

Why Beet ?

- > High Energy/Me
- > High utilisation 90%+ compared with Kale (70-80%)
- > High yield 20t+
- > Environmental Benefit? Low protein
- > Easy to grow in Canterbury

Why Not Beet ?

- > Low Protein
- > Low fibre
- > Low in minerals
- > High risk stock management crop (wet weather, acidosis)
- > High soil ingestion
- > Establishment cost

Why Swedes?

- > High in protein
- > Lower risk stock management
- > Acceptable yield 18t DM/Ha
- > High utilisation
- > High mineral content, less supplementation P, Se

Why not Swedes?

- > Animal Health (glucosinolates, nitrates)
- > Lower yields in comparison to Beet per Ha
- > Susceptible to disease and insects
- > Water requirement

Conclusion

- > Farmers will always want different options
- > Some are comfortable with high risk, some not
- > For us, simple systems are the priority with multiple farms

The Farming Consultant: Miranda Hunter, Roslyn Consultancy Ltd

Presenter key points:

1. Mixed messages re benefits/costs of supplementary feed — communication
2. Sustainability of winter brassica/fodder beet production
3. Faster crop establishment requiring lower inputs
4. Management of on-farm nutrient loss from winter grazing
5. Impact of milking platform supplements on effluent and manure management
6. Integration of supplementary feeds across whole operation — winter grazing and lactation
7. Time lag for implementation of research findings in applied on-farm models

A Farm Consultant's Perspective

Presentation - Miranda Hunter

Roslyn Consultancy Ltd

So who am I?

Background

- ▶ Dairy farming
- ▶ Extension (with dairy farmers)
- ▶ Linking with research (dairy farm systems)

Current Work

- ▶ Dairy farm system environmental consultancy (with dairy farmers, industry and government)
- ▶ Overseas consultancy (with dairy farmers under MFAT programme)

Roslyn Consultancy Ltd

Scope of presentation

- ▶ Dairy farming (whole farm system)
- ▶ Southern South Island (predominately Southland)
- ▶ Environmental (within whole farm system)
- ▶ Tend to focus at more the applied end!

Roslyn Consultancy Ltd

This presentation

- ▶ Current situation for farmers
- ▶ Feed supply (with a wintering focus)
- ▶ Wintering
 - ▶ Current situation
 - ▶ Medium term
 - ▶ Long term
 - ▶ Ideal
- ▶ Summary

Roslyn Consultancy Ltd

Feed Supply - Wintering

Wintering is key element in farm system (in the Southern South Island)

- ▶ Productive and reproductive
- ▶ Cost
- ▶ Environmental

Roslyn Consultancy Ltd

Current situation

Farm system

- ▶ Mixed messages around supplementary feeding and the economics

People

- ▶ Skilled staff
- ▶ Migrant staff and visas
- ▶ Increased skills

Animals

- ▶ Public interest and awareness

Roslyn Consultancy Ltd

Current situation

Environmental

- ▶ Nutrient loss from milking platform vs whole farm business
- ▶ Lack of certainty - business risk
- ▶ Requirements for capital

Research

- ▶ Work coming through
- ▶ Models (eg Overseer)

Roslin Consultancy Ltd

Current situation

Financially on farm

- ▶ Range in operating surpluses
- ▶ Banks
 - ▶ Real focus on reducing debt levels
- ▶ Expect interest and principle to be paid

Roslin Consultancy Ltd

Impact of Investment on farming business

BEMP = milk price per kilogram of milk solids required for a cash budget to achieve a cash surplus of \$0.

- ▶ Income -
 - ▶ Milk
- ▶ Expenditure (Cash expenditure items)
 - ▶ Farm working expenses (FWE)
 - ▶ Interest and rent
 - ▶ Drawings
 - ▶ Tax
 - ▶ Capital expenditure.

Impact of BEMP

	\$4.80 BEMP	\$5.50 BEMP	\$6.20 BEMP
Milk income	\$5.75	\$5.75	\$5.75
BEMP	\$4.80	\$5.50	\$6.20
Livestock sales	\$.35	\$.35	\$.35
Surplus	\$1.30	\$0.60	(\$0.10)
Surplus (eg 240,000 kg ms) (shareholder dividends, repay debt)	\$312,000	\$144,000	(\$24,000)

Adding Investment

- ▶ Example
 - ▶ Spends \$3000 per cow off paddock structure
 - ▶ Interest rate of 6% over a 20 year period
 - ▶ - adds 65c to their breakeven milk price

(simple - no account costs of making supplements, feed requirements, value of nutrients)

	\$4.80 BEMP	\$5.50 BEMP	\$6.20 BEMP
Milk income	\$5.75	\$5.75	\$5.75
BEMP	\$4.80	\$5.50	\$6.20
Livestock sales	\$.35	\$.35	\$.35
Surplus	\$1.30	\$0.60	(\$0.10)
Surplus (eg 240,000 kg ms) (shareholder dividends, repay debt)	\$312,000	\$144,000	(\$24,000)

Financial Implications

- ▶ Spending
 - ▶ Limited ability
 - ▶ Targeted – whole farm systems context

Wintering - Current Situation

- ▶ Reliance on paddock wintering (brassica and fodder beet crops)
 - ▶ Seen as cost effective
 - ▶ Known / skills
 - ▶ Sustainability of cop rotations
 - ▶ Nutrient loss
 - ▶ Public perception / animal welfare

Roslin Consultancy Ltd

Wintering - Current Situation (cont)

- ▶ Off paddock structures increased significantly over last 10 years
 - ▶ Significant amounts of imported supplements into milking platforms
 - ▶ Feed quality variable
 - ▶ BCS
 - ▶ Large capital investment - farm system change
 - ▶ Effluents and manures
 - ▶ Soil tests
 - ▶ Skills required

Roslin Consultancy Ltd

Wintering - Medium Term

- ▶ GMP
- ▶ Sustainable crop rotations
- ▶ Fertiliser and N applied to forage crops (linked to yield)
- ▶ Off paddock facilities
 - ▶ Feed options
 - ▶ Effluents and manures

Need:

Link R, D and E – farmers getting consistency of message

Practical application

Link to environmental targets

Roslin Consultancy Ltd

Wintering - Long Term

- ▶ Feeds - lower nutrient loss (including in situ grazing)
- ▶ Resilient farm systems
 - ▶ Feed options
 - ▶ Feeds that grow more (or the same) for less inputs
 - ▶ Integration of feeds into the whole farm system – both lactation and wintering
 - ▶ Improved capability of both farmers and support people

Roslin Consultancy Ltd

Winter Feeds - whole farm system ideal

- ▶ Targeted
 - ▶ Soil type, contour, climate
 - ▶ Grazing, cut and carry, ensiling
 - ▶ GMP
- ▶ Lower nutrient loss
- ▶ Same (or more) for less inputs - a cost effective feed
- ▶ Grows quickly and reliably – time land out
- ▶ Rotation sustainable
- ▶ Skills levels
- ▶ Animals

Roslin Consultancy Ltd

Summary

- ▶ Farmers - significant challenges (financial, environmental, animal welfare)
- ▶ Banks focused debt repayment
- ▶ Huge range skill levels - farmers and rural professionals
- ▶ Farmers (RPs) need good and clear information
- ▶ Wintering feed supply critical (esp Southern S Is)
- ▶ Opportunity for improvement on current practices
- ▶ New technology winter feeds targeted for specific situations key
- ▶ Need any work linked into whole farm systems context (not component)

Roslin Consultancy Ltd

The Corporate Farming Enterprise: Paul McGill (Landcorp)

Presenter key points:

1. Crop management; Agronomic & nutritionally for feeding to animals
2. Viability; cost of supplement / crop fed
3. Environmental; nutrient uptake, losses from grazing
4. Lifecycle analysis (LCA); Energy & GHGs
5. Multi use; It may be in the future that the crop is harvested to extract plant components and the by-products of this process used for stock supplement

OUR CONSUMER

PĀMU
FARMS OF
NEW ZEALAND

FUTURE

PĀMU
FARMS OF
NEW ZEALAND

PĀMU
FARMS OF
NEW ZEALAND

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Group discussion session

1. Define potential scenarios (2-3) for how your challenge or opportunity might play out over the next 10 years.
2. Determine the likely impacts on farming of each scenario.
3. Identify how supplementary feed crops might need to change to support / mitigate these scenarios.

Develop a 10-year roadmap of R&D outcomes needed to make these changes – what do we need to achieve by when.

General considerations:

- Ability of people on farm to adopt and manage new systems
- Primary focus on brassica and cereal forage, but identify if other supplementary feed crops need additional focus.

Social and biosecurity pressures around imported feeds.

<p>Group 1: Reduce environmental impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrient uptake - Catch crops - Nutrient losses 	<p>Group 4: Fitting with redesigned farm systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adoption of winter feedpads - Cut and carry systems - Harvest considerations, timing of harvest, storage of harvested product
<p>Group 2: Improve feed / nutritional content</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yield and utilisation - Animal safety - Functional diversity - Enhanced milk/meat composition - Plant extracts 	<p>Group 5: Improved animal health and new concerns around animal welfare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimising health risks: nitrates, bloat, acidosis - Societal concerns around animal personality, emotions and experiences
<p>Group 3: Improved agronomic performance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disease and pest resistance - Establishment time - Resilience to climate variability - Water use efficiency / drought tolerance - Life cycle analysis / energy efficiency 	<p>Group 6: Managing greenhouse gas emissions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mitigation potential - Animal efficiency

Verbal reporting back session

A few key themes arose, frequently from more than one or even all of the Groups:

- **Regulatory** aspects are going to be more important and more direct. Including right to farm and right of way-to-farm.
- **Animal and environmental welfare** – often conflicting in themselves and different parts of population differ in expectations.
- In particular, two related scenarios indicated – ban/regulation of **winter grazing** and **housed animals**. Clearly interlinked and will affect types and nature of crops grown (all or larger proportion of cut and carry feed, more stored feed types, reduction in single feed for days at a time, shift from feed as binary ME or rprotein, and include fibre measure. Will lead to more effluent management requirements and associated nutrients (especially housed animals as capture all excreta). Capital requirements for infrastructure – not just sheds, but excreta manage, feed supply and storage.
- LUS concept (**Land Use Suitability**) – but broader to right crop/right place/right time/right animal. Could lead to **shared use of farm landscape** – within collaborative private ownership or corporatisation. More specialisation of management expertise for different components of the system.

Group report back sessions, examples of notes and some extended narrative

Photographs taken of the reporting back session notes (Figure 2 shows two examples) were collated into common theme areas. This collation was done twice in an attempt to avoid selection bias. Both collations are included here as they indicate slightly different interpretations of some points and the broader theme they address.

Collation 1

Mixed farm systems – more than one enterprise/farm activity in a more complex landscape, range of systems depending on catchment capacity, lower dairy intensive management, aquaculture or other very different systems compatible

Reduced environmental impacts – large infrastructure investments, closed systems (housed, better nutrient catch and controlled distribution), no tillage crops, efficiency of nutrient use, better tools to determine nutrient requirements and losses, water quality care, OVERSEER® or similar extend to more management scenarios including supplementary feeds and economic/environment values, monitoring to reduce impacts but retain profitability and resilience, impacts on soil quality, reduced water requirements especially irrigation, imported feed risks (supply chain, biosecurity), no winter crop grazing

New developments – e-cow models, better/different cow breeding (high productivity, lower methane, nitrogen outputs), new crop types and management for feed (low nitrogen content, high productivity, multi-species crops, different silage crops, resolving cut & carry volume/water difficulties, mixed farms, precision agriculture, reduced fallow land time, more diverse paddocks and crops, better understanding and opportunities from rhizosphere microbes, feeds with different feed values, better match between supply and demand profiles of crops, more choice in crop destinations (e.g. seed, grazing, green manure, stored feed), better defined management of crop production (e.g. physical/environment, nutrient, protection chemicals etc), new rotation schemes, move towards direct crop to human food products, more winter active crop choices, fodder beet virus threat to crop viability, other new diseases/weed incursions, emissions trading scheme extends to agriculture

Right to farm/social licence – more authenticity/transparency, animal welfare (especially glucosinolates in brassica, acidosis with fodder beet)

Management – greater demand for skilled advisors, managers and staff, better information on values and uses of forages/supplementary feeds, increased utilisation of supplementary/silage feeding systems, higher % utilisation percentage of feeds, better understanding of feed supply security, feed quality health and productivity effects on animals, ergot management, crop secondary compounds modify milk/meat

Infrastructure – closed systems, housed, fencing and drainage, effluent storage and application, recycling nutrients better,

R&D – more demonstration farms, more opportunities for farmer involvement, extend information from areas with good results, more explicit implementation plans, determine optimal yield targets for feed crops, quality and feed value targets.

Collation 2

<p>Environmental impact</p> <p>Winter crop grazing regulation Cut & carry/ housed animals Effluent storage and use No-till fodder beet/brassica establishment Catch drops for winter N capture Agriculture enters ETS</p>	<p>Animal health</p> <p>Brassica glucosinolates, nitrates Acidosis, e.g. fodder beet Ergot management Winter feed with fibre Multicrop systems, multispecies and/or mix of grazing and supplements Controlled grazing and off paddock feed (infrastructure investment) Housed animals (infrastructure investment) Automated systems, digital tools, monitoring Distance to crops Shelter for animals</p>
<p>Crop variety and quality</p> <p>Silage quality (WCS) 90% of brassica crop utilisation by animals target Winter feed with fibre Stored crop – quality, longevity Suitability for feed pad use Improved harvest window of crops Pasture based silage increasing pastoral pests Frugal crops – low nutrient and water use Multicrop systems, multispecies and/or mix of grazing and supplements</p>	<p>Education</p> <p>More complex farm systems, especially cropping mix Regulatory tools – understanding and use Improved modelling tools Other farm ownership and land management options Arable and Pastoral farm systems integrated</p>
<p>Market access</p> <p>Non-tariff barriers Brand and brand image (housed/feed pad) Consumer shift to direct plant food consumption</p>	<p>Financial</p> <p>Reduced intensity and more land Infrastructure – housing, feed pad, effluent management Feed supply – security, quality, cost Increased supplementary feed utilisation: waste ratio</p>

ASSOCIATED MATERIAL

The Pastoral Industry Forage Strategy (2 pages) and associated Discussion Document (64 pages) developed during 2017 provide a considerably broader context and information.

<https://beeflambnz.com/your-levies-at-work/national-forage-strategy>

Reproduced below is the “Risk Management Guide for Intensive Winter Grazing on Arable Farms” developed under a Sustainable Farming Fund project, with permission FAR.

Risk Management Guide for Intensive Winter Grazing on Arable Farms

Instructions: Answer 'yes' or 'no' to having each risk factor in your winter grazing system. For each factor you answered 'yes' to, see what the associated risks are of nitrate leaching, phosphorus (P) and sediment losses, and soil damage through compaction and pugging. Risk management options relevant to each risk factor are listed in the last column and refer to the table on the next page.

yes/no	Risk factor	Risk of nitrate leaching	Risk of P and sediment losses	Risk of compaction and pugging	Risk management options
	Light soils (sandy, stony)	x			1
	Heavy soils		x	x	1, 2, 4, 6
	Poor soil structure		x	x	1, 2, 4, 6
	Steep slopes		x		1, 4, 5
	Critical sources (waterways, natural drainage streams)		x		1, 5, 6
	High stocking density (cows/ha/day)	x		x	3, 6
	High soil residual N levels	x			1, 2, 3
	High protein level in feed	x			3, 6
	Lack of knowledge or skills in staff managing winter grazing	x	x	x	1, 5, 6
	Consecutive winter cropping	x	x	x	2
	High rainfall (all above risk factors are intensified with high rainfall)	x	x	x	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6

Ministry for Primary Industries
Manatū Ahu Matua

This project was supported with funding from the Ministry for Primary Industries Sustainable Farming Fund.

Risk Management Options

	Some paddocks may need to be avoided completely
	Only graze high risk areas in dry conditions
1. PADDOCK AWARENESS	Graze heavier soils early in the season before they get saturated, and light soils later in the season after the biggest risk of drainage
	Begin grazing at the top of the slope and work downhill
	When near waterways, begin grazing away from the critical source and work towards it, leaving at least a 3 meter buffer zone
	Allow paddocks to recover between grazing events (soils prone to compaction should have longer periods between winter forage crops)
2. CROP ROTATION AND CULTIVATION	Fit the crop rotation so that it helps break weed, disease, and pest cycles
	Minimise tillage before and after the forage crop
	Sow a crop that can utilise remaining N in soil (cereals, grass) as soon as soil conditions are suitable
3. CROP SELECTION AND MANAGEMENT	Manage fertiliser inputs to forage crop to meet crop demand
	If grazing a high yielding crop, use reactive management strategies (see number 6)
	Graze a lower yielding crop (Italian ryegrass, forage oats) to decrease stocking density requirements
	Understand nutritional qualities of crops, and supplement accordingly (e.g. kale is high in protein but low in fibre, so supplement needs fibre but not protein)
4. FEED PREPARATION	Place bales of straw or baleage throughout paddock for break feeding to eliminate the need to drive heavy equipment on vulnerable soils
	Lift fodder beet in dry conditions and feed off the paddock when needed
5. STAFF TRAINING	Ensure staff responsible for managing grazing are up-skilled with management strategies to react in wet conditions (see number 6)
	Set up guidelines in a contract if staff from off-farm are managing grazing
	Shift more than once a day with small breaks before soil begins pugging
6. MANAGING GRAZING ON WET SOILS	Increase amount of supplement fed, and feed out in less vulnerable areas
	Back fence and use transportable water troughs to minimise hoof traffic on bare soils
	Split the mob into multiple groups to reduce grazing density
	Have a stand-off paddock or pad in very wet conditions

Ministry for Primary Industries
Manatū Ahu Matua

This project was supported with funding from the Ministry for Primary Industries Sustainable Farming Fund.

PARTICIPANTS

Facilitator:	Craig Osborne	
DairyNZ:	Ina Pinxterhuis (presenter) Dawn Dalley Virginia Serra	
FAR:	Ivan Lawrie (presenter) Abie Horrocks	
Lincoln University:	Pablo Gregorini (presenter)	
Regional Councils:	Ian Brown (presenter) (Ecan) Bala TikkiSETTY (Waikato Regional Council) Ewen Rodway (Environment Southland)	
Farmer:	Mark Slee (presenter)	
Farm Advisor:	Miranda Hunter (presenter)	
Landcorp:	Paul McGill (presenter)	
Beef+Lamb:	Geoff Ridley	
PGG Wrightson Seeds Ltd:	Fiona Foley Charlotte Westwood Al Moorhead Ben Trotter John McKenzie Hamish Mulcock David Green	Andrew Dumbleton Wayne Nichol Glenn Judson Derek Woodfield Damian Lynch Sarah McKenzie
PFR:	Bill Griffin Paul Johnston Mary Christey Simon Bulman John de Ruyter Edmar Teixeira Shane Maley Sarah Bromley	Andy Hay Fernand Kenel Samantha Baldwin Paul Johnstone Brendon Malcolm Wei Hu Warrick Nelson